

The impacts of Revolution: Are we progressing or regressing?

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Abstract

The world today is changing rapidly from the one even a decade ago. This change has impacted human life both positively and negatively. Revolutions in the evolutions of false needs and dictatorship of commodities have altered the mapping of life of all. Poverty, inequality, injustice and lack of basic needs form the ground for a revolutionary upheaval. Besides this political revolution silently there has been another revolution. Almost everywhere man is now treated either as a client or as a consumer. The decline in the genuine feeling of sharing and caring is alarming. The concept of trades and commerce has been changed radically with digitalization. Man has forgotten to cultivate his intuition, nurture his god gifted talents in arts and creativity. Virtual teachers have replaced the physical teachers. Everywhere the relation seems to be valued in terms of economy. Humanoid robots are seen to assist the needy. This is revolution. But there is another revolution. Now a family of three members is seen conversing amongst them using cell phones. Once incurable diseases are now cured fast. But the surge of dishonest medicos and middlemen is ruinous. The very questions ‘are we progressing or regressing?’ naturally surface everywhere.

Key words:

Revolution, Dictatorship of commodities, Thought process, Dependence on tools, Virtual teachers, Human Identity,

Introduction

The world today is changing rapidly bad beyond recognition from the one even a decade ago. This change has impacted human life both positively and negatively. The run for materialistic advancement looks sometimes as fun for majority of the populace who fails to earn the basics. Revolutions in the evolutions of false needs coined with greed and feeds of dictatorship of commodities have altered the mapping of life of all- small or tall. It is an admitted truth that poverty, inequality, injustice and lack of basic needs form the ground for a revolutionary upheaval in a country and it develops with time in the mind of the affected masses for radical alteration in basic values and beliefs. This is the irresistible trend of civilization or the showcase of the stage of advancement of human’s social and cultural development. But a balance is a must between the artificiality and the naturality. This is because despite our best knowledge/skill our foolishness of distancing us from the naturality may cause havoc and lead all the revolutionary developments achieved so far to a big zero. The quote of Bertrand Russell may be seen in this regard-

“Broadly speaking, we are in the middle of a race between human skill as a means and human folly as an end.” (1)

Revolutions in different spheres

Man’s thought process has been changed remarkably. He is no more as simple as before. He has been forced to change his simplicity, faith and confidence in fellow beings by being cheated, duped and betrayed again and again by the sheer commercial mentality of the people around. Almost

everywhere he is now treated either as a client or as a consumer. Though painful it is to note but it's a fact that human behavior has had a radical change over a few decades. This is also revolution but in a regressive way. Human identity has been losing fast to the identities attached by the business houses. Pains and sufferings hardly find balms of sincere love and empathy; rather these are often seen to be encashed by a section of people to serve their pecuniary enhancement. Even the close persons are no exceptions. They too are guided in most cases by the relation of reciprocal interests. The decline in the genuine feeling of sharing and caring is now alarmingly apparent. There seems to be a revolution in our erstwhile traditional values that preaches the principle of Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam or "the world is one family". The journey of advancement towards material excellence and degradation in moral and humanistic attitude is seen to run parallel and has followed a series of revolution. Still to keep humanity smiling forever, the observation of Dr. Suresh PB on 'Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam' may be seen in this regard from the following-

"The quote "Vasudeva Kutumbakam" is a powerful reminder of our shared humanity and our responsibility to each other. It is a message of hope and unity that is needed more than ever in today's world. The world is one family.

We are all connected, regardless of our nationality, race, religion, or ethnicity. We share the same planet, and we have a responsibility to care for it and for each other.

Let us come together as one family and work to solve the challenges that we face, such as climate change, poverty, and inequality. Let us build a better future for all of us." (2)

Modern men are now too much dependant on tools. Man's drudgeries have been lessened miraculously due to revolutionary inventions made in the recent past. Besides science revolution in the field of commerce and industry is also notable. Online business has made its entry in almost every sector of trades and industries. Even the tea stalls on the footpath carry paperless transaction through scanners pasted on the walls. In the Indian perspective never ever the commoners were seen using online services like Amazon, flipkart, blinkit, Zomato etc sitting on their drawing rooms and availing the facilities of online deliveries as they are doing now. People are now no more required to carry cash with them for shopping. Their handy digital mobile phone is sufficient to cater their needs. People can now communicate face to face through their screens on all important topics both of professional and educational importance through a video conference meeting sitting in different locations, thereby saving both time and money. With advancement of science and technology as well as strong social Medias like face book, you tubes, whatsApp people are now seen earning lakhs of rupees through selling/ promoting contents on these virtual platforms, often staying at home and using their free time. The concept of trades and commerce has thus been changed radically from the one a few decades earlier. But what about creativity, spontaneity or the poetry, the song of the mind! The revolution thus looks both welcome and unwelcome depending largely on its utilization by legislators/the men in power for the welfare of the masses. The observation of Benjamin Constant may be read in this regard as follows:

"The work of the legislator is not complete when he has simply brought peace to the people. Even when the populace is satisfied, there is much left to do. Institutions must carry out the moral education of the citizens. By respecting their individual rights, securing their independence, refraining from troubling their work, institutions must nevertheless dedicate themselves to influencing public affairs, calling on the people to contribute to the exercise of power through their decisions and their votes, guaranteeing their right of control and supervision through the

expression of their opinions, and by shaping them up through the exercise of these high functions, give them both the desire and the power to perform them.” (3)

With rapid urbanization and emergence of nuclear family in contrast with the rural enclosures and erstwhile joint family everywhere there has been radical change or revolution in the livelihood of the people. Nowadays next door neighbors look unknown whereas people living within the radius of a few kilometers were known by name even a few decades ago. With advancement of science and technology our life style has been changed radically. Humanoid robots are seen to assist elderly people in their household work and to provide company to overcome their loneliness. Yes, this is revolution indeed. But there is another revolution. Now a family of three members is often seen conversing amongst them using their cell phone sitting in a sofa of the drawing room but without a talk or save eye contact. Machine steals more attention than human beings and as it looks to do work fast and accurate, people are seen embracing it dearly than the dear ones. The observation of Arooj Kanwal may be seen in this regard from the following-

“Artificial intelligence has revolutionized the world. It can be a blessing making our life super easy or it can be a curse because it makes humans useless. It has made so many things so easy and accessible that sometimes it looks unreal to get your work done in minutes without any errors.” (4)

Revolutions in the medical fields have had its tremendous impact on the longevity of the mankind with innovations of gene editing technology, wearable technology and telemedicine. Nowadays transplantation of organs has become very easy. Once incurable diseases are now cured within very short period by using regenerative therapy treatment. All these developments take the civilization onto the path of pride and glory. But there runs simultaneously a parallel cycle of money making by some medicos and a racket of middlemen who feels no compunction playing with the patients like guinea pigs. This is certainly not a sign of hope for the future. Revolutions have had its way in both directions. The very mentality of becoming an upstart seems to be the main cause behind it. Besides, the more we have got, the more we have become demanding. We have forgotten to be satisfied with what we have. Instead we have started to take away others' share. This is why humanity is at risk. The following may be seen in this regard-

'No other gift is greater than the gift of life! The patient may doubt his relatives, his sons and even his parents, but he has full faith in his physician. He gives himself up in the doctor's hands and has no misgivings about him. Therefore, it is the physician's duty to look after him as his own.' (5)

Replacement of god or great thinkers of the world like Krishna, Christ, Mohammed, Aristotle, Confucius, Kant and others looks like a trend of the present generation. Forgetful of the essence and fragrance of their great teachings men are now seen developing negative human qualities more than the positive ones. There seems to be a spiritual revolution to have taken place everywhere; but in the negative way. The attributes of a true human being like love, kindness, sacrifice, honesty, fellow feeling and other nobler elements are on the wane. Bigotry, fanaticism, cruelty, atrocities, gross violation of humanity etc are nothing new but the known picture of the society around. These are all for money. Money always rules the world. It's a fact. But the madness for aggrandizement or the mentality for earning money by any means- fair or foul is on the rise with a galloping rate. Really we have had a revolution where the difference of income between the poor and the rich has widened

unimaginably during a few decades. This being the reality, in order to make humanity smiling, needed is again a look into the philosophy of the great champions of humanity. Enlightenment of mind, the gift of any spiritual revolution is an impulsive force to push civilization to a meaningful height. The observation of Dmitri Itskov on the effects of a spiritual revolution as experienced over the history of human civilization may be perused from the following –

“A spiritual revolution means a wide program for the transformation of the individual and mass consciousness, according to which:

– negative human qualities will be taken under control: aggression towards others, excessively egoistic aspirations, unrestrained consumerism, inertia;

– positive qualities will be brought out: inner purity, beauty, sympathy, love for all living beings, harmony, altruism, the ability to serve the good of society, sacrifice and commitment;

“The first spiritual revolution was the period when over an extremely short space of time, great thinkers arose: Buddha, Confucius, Socrates, Plato, Christ and Mohammed – a radical humanist revolution in the spiritual life of human beings. Civilization gained systems of values and goals that enabled humankind to overcome the “catastrophe of the bronze age”, the potential of which has not been exhausted to this day. ..(6)

Conclusion

Revolution or a radical change is therefore not confined to political order in favor of self rule or equality or justice but it stands for the fundamental change from the long and outdated concept to the newly and time demanded exercise to take the civilization onto the roads of progress with smiling populace all around. Everywhere there has been a silent revolution in the thought process of all unlike a few decades ago. Man has forgotten to cultivate his intuition, nurture his god gifted talents in arts and creativity. Virtual teachers have replaced the physical teachers. The bond between the teachers and the taught looks loosened. Everywhere the relation seems to be valued in terms of economy as opposed to one based on love, respect and obligation to societal needs. But do we not witness it in our daily life? Does the present generation enjoy smiling environment all around? Does it not miss the warmth of connectivity with others? Can human intelligence be replaced altogether by the artificial intelligence? The very questions ‘are we progressing or regressing?’ naturally surface everywhere.

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Bio-note:

A science graduate and a retired Accounts Official in Indian Railways, Biswanath Kundu (b.1963) is an author of fifteen books, seven of them being books of poems. His poems and articles have been published in different prestigious anthologies and internationally famous journals. His latest book titled Critical Sensibilities: Insightful Appraisals, published by Authorspress, New Delhi is a collection of literary studies

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